

Esters of Selenous Acid

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Ethyl selenite has been prepared by the azeotropic dehydration of selenous acid and several higher esters have been prepared from ethyl selenite by the alcohol-interchange technique. Reactions of ethyl selenite with normal alcohols result in the dialkyl selenites, whereas in the case of secondary and tertiary alcohols mixed esters are formed by the replacement of one ethoxyl group only.

Earlier attempts to prepare the esters of selenous acid were made to resolve the controversy between the two possible structures for this acid:

The first attempt appears to have been made by Michaleis and Landmann¹ by employing the reaction:

Almost simultaneously the preparation of ethyl selenite was described by Orndroff² by the reaction between sodium ethoxide and selenyl chloride:

Strecker and Daniel³ showed spectrochemically that the methyl, ethyl, and propyl esters, prepared by the above two techniques, were identical.

Melnikov and Rokitskaya⁴ showed that the different alkyl esters could be obtained by treating selenium dioxide with alcohols and thus they prepared the methyl, ethyl, propyl, butyl, and isoamyl esters:

(where R is methyl, ethyl, propyl, butyl, and isoamyl radical).

Kaufmann and Spannuth⁵ prepared higher monoalkylmonohydroxy and dialkyl esters by treating selenium dioxide with higher alcohols:

1. *Annalen*, 1887, 241, 150.
2. *Amer. Chem. J.*, 1887, 9, 462.
3. *Annalen*, 1928, 462, 186.
4. *J. Gen. Chem.*, 1937, 7, 1532.
5. *Chem. Ber.*, 1958, 91, 2127.

(where R is decyl, dodecyl, tetradecyl, and hexadecyl radical). The higher selenium esters on treatment with methanol furnished the methyl ester :

Dubrovina⁶ isolated the ethyl selenite by treating antimony triethoxide with selenium dioxide:

Hesse and Majumdar⁷ obtained dimethyl and monomethylmonoethyl selenites by the dropwise addition of solutions of selenium dioxide in methanol and ethanol, respectively, to the diazomethane solution in light petroleum with cooling at -5° .

Methyl ester was also obtained⁸ by treating selenium dioxide in absolute methanol with diazoethyl acetate:

A considerable amount of work has been published from these laboratories during the last few years on the alkoxide derivatives of metals⁹⁻¹³ and non-metals¹⁴⁻¹⁶. The azeotropic distillation technique was applied successfully in the synthesis of ethyl borate¹⁷ from which higher alkyl borates were prepared in quantitative yields by alcohol-interchange technique. In view of the success achieved in the above work, it was considered worthwhile to make a systematic and comparative study of alkyl selenites also by similar techniques.

Ethyl selenite has been prepared by the azeotropic dehydration of selenous acid with ethanol and benzene. It has been further used as the starting material for the preparation of various higher esters by alcohol-interchange technique in presence of benzene:

6. *U'yanavelena*, 1956, 2, 3-70.

7. *Chem. Ber.*, 1960, 93, 1129.

8. Bradley *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 3450.

9. Mehrotra, *this Journal*, 1953, 30, 585; 1954 31, 85.

10. Puri *et al.*, *J. Less-Common Metals*, 1962, 4, 393.

11. Mehrotra, *this Journal*, 1954, 31, 904.

12. Mehrotra and Mittal, *Z. anorg. allgem. Chem.* (communicated).

13. Mehrotra and Kapoor, *J. Less-Common Metals* (communicated).

14. Mehrotra and Srivastava, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 1032.

15. Mehrotra and Narain, *this Journal*, 1962, 39, 855.

16. Mehrotra and Chandra, *ibid.*, 1962, 39, 235.

17. Webster and Dennis, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 55, 3233.

Reactions with normal alcohols result in the formation of dialkyl selenites, whereas those with secondary and tertiary alcohols yield the mixed esters with the replacement of only one alkoxy group:

where R = methyl, *n*-propyl, *n*-butyl, isobutyl, isoamyl, and *n*-hexyl radicals and R' = isopropyl, *sec*-butyl, *t*-butyl, and *t*-amyl radicals).

EXPERIMENTAL

The reactions were carried out in all-glass apparatus with standard joints (Quickfit) and with careful exclusion of moisture. For fractionation, a long column, packed with Raschig rings and fitted to a total-condensation variable take-off still head, was used.

Benzene was dried over sodium wire and finally by azeotropic distillation with ethanol. Ethanol was dried first by refluxing over quick lime and then by distilling over sodium ethoxide; the final drying was accomplished azeotropically with benzene. Isopropanol was first dried over metallic sodium and was finally fractionated over aluminium isopropoxide. *n*-Propanol, butanols (*n. sec.*, and *t*), amyl alcohols (*iso* and *t*), and *n*-hexanol were dried by distilling over the corresponding sodium alkoxides and carefully fractionated. Methanol was dried by distilling over magnesium ribbon in presence of iodine. Selenous acid employed was an E. Merck product.

Selenium was estimated in the elementary form, using sulphur dioxide in hydrochloric acid as the precipitating agent.

The alkoxy content was estimated in ethoxy and isopropoxy derivatives by hydrolysing the compound with alkali in presence of benzene. The ethanol and isopropanol liberated were fractionated azeotropically and estimated by an oxidimetric method⁶.

Ethyl Selenite.—To selenous acid (10 g.) were added an excess of ethanol and benzene. A clear solution was obtained. The reaction was endothermic. The contents were slowly refluxed for about half an hour under a column (bath temp. 110–20°) and the ternary azeotrope of water, alcohol, and benzene (at 65°) was slowly collected. This was repeated several times till the distilling liquid did not show any tendency of lowering below 68°. Refluxing was continued and the excess of alcohol and benzene were removed under the column. A colorless liquid distilling at 76°/10 mm was obtained by evaporating the excess solvent under reduced pressure at the room temperature; yield of the undistilled product was 13 g. (91%) and of the distilled product, 12 g. (84%). [Found: Se, 42.95; OEt, 48.76. Calc. for $\text{OSe}(\text{OEt})_2$: Se, 42.66; OEt, 48.68%].

Higher Alkyl Selenites from Ethyl Selenite by Alcohol-interchange Technique.—*n*-Propanol (22.64 g.) was added to ethyl selenite (2.326 g.), followed by benzene. The reaction was endothermic. The contents were refluxed under a column for 16 hours and the ethanol was removed azeotropically with benzene (at 68°). Excess of the benzene

and of the alcohol were distilled and the contents on drying under reduced pressure at the room temperature provided a colorless liquid distilling at $104^{\circ}/7.5\text{mm}$; yield 2.435 g., (91%). [Found: Se, 37.09. Calc. for $\text{OSe}(\text{OPr}^n)_2$: Se, 37.05%].

For brevity the reactions with other primary alcohols are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I
Reactions of ethyl selenite with normal alcohols.

Reactants.	Product.	Yield.	%Selenium.		Reflux time.
			Found.	Calc.	
Et selenite (2.53g.) + <i>n</i> -butanol (23.16g.)	<i>n</i> -Butyl selenite; light yellow liquid distilling at $110^{\circ}/7\text{mm}$	2.785 g. (82%)	32.96	32.73	10 hr.
Et selenite (2.80g.) + isobutanol (13.84g.)	Isobutyl selenite; colorless liquid distilling at $106^{\circ}/4.5\text{mm}$	2.870 (85%)	32.71	32.73	10
Et selenite (2.50g.) + isamyl alcohol (10.75g.)	Isamyl selenite; light yellow liquid distilling at $122^{\circ}/3.5\text{mm}$	3.190 (85%)	29.37	29.76	8
Et selenite (2.13g.) + <i>n</i> -hexyl alcohol (16.29g.)	<i>n</i> -Hexyl selenite; light yellow liquid distilling at $140^{\circ}/2\text{mm}$	2.830 (83%)	26.25	26.60	8

In spite of continuous and careful fractionation, the corresponding reactions with secondary and tertiary alcohols resulted in the replacement of only one of the ethoxyl groups and mixed esters only could be prepared in these cases. The data are recorded in Table II.

TABLE II
Reactions of ethyl selenite with secondary and tertiary alcohols.

Reactants.	Products.	Yield.	%Selenium.		Alcohol in azeotrope.		Reflux time.
			Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	
Et selenite (2.80g.) + isopropanol (10.82g.)	Monoethyl mono-isopropyl selenite; colorless liquid distilling at $78^{\circ}/5\text{mm}$	2.840 g. (91%)	39.34	39.65	..	..	8 hr.
Et selenite (1.65g.) + <i>sec</i> -butanol (15.79g.)	Monoethyl mono- <i>sec</i> - butyl selenite; colorless liquid distilling at $101^{\circ}/7\text{mm}$	1.630 (86%)	36.73	37.06	..	..	8
Et selenite (2.33g.) + <i>t</i> -butanol (11.13g.)	Monoethyl mono- <i>t</i> -butyl selenite; decomposes on distillation	2.605 (90%)	38.13	37.06	0.57 g.	0.0581 g.	13
Et selenite (2.92g.) + <i>t</i> -amyl alcohol (27.48g.)	Monoethyl mono- <i>t</i> -amyl selenite; decomposes on distillation	3.155 (90%)	34.00	34.80	0.74	0.742	12

Monomethyl Monoethyl Selenite.—To ethyl selenite (3.32 g.) was added methanol (0.574 g., 1*M*) and the contents were subjected to distillation. A colorless liquid distilled at $70^{\circ}/8\text{mm}$; yield 2.15 g (70%). [Found; Se, 45.78. Calc for $(\text{OMe})(\text{OEt})\text{SeO}$: Se, 46.19%].

Methyl Selenite.—To ethyl selenite (6.10 g.) was added an excess of methanol, followed by benzene. A detectable endothermic reaction occurred. The contents were subjected to

distillation and the process repeated several times till the distilling liquid did not show any tendency of raising the temperature above 57° . A colorless liquid distilling at $67^{\circ}/10\text{mm}$ was obtained on drying the contents under reduced pressure at the room temperature. Yield of the undistilled product was 3.56g (67%); distilled product, 2.45 g. (46%). The yield was low as some of the product was carried away by the distillate. Found: Se, 50.2. Calc. for $\text{OSe}(\text{OMe})_2$: Se, 50.2%].

Isopropyl Selenite.—Selenious acid (5 g.) was dissolved in excess of isopropanol, followed by the addition of benzene. The reaction was endothermic. The contents were slowly refluxed under a column for an hour (bath temp. $110-20^{\circ}$). The ternary azeotrope of isopropanol, benzene, and water was slowly collected at 66.7° . This was repeated several times till the distilling liquid did not show any tendency of lowering the temperature below 71.9° . Excess of the alcohol and benzene were distilled. The contents were dried at the pump at the room temperature to provide a colorless liquid, distilling at $88^{\circ}/4.5\text{mm}$. Yield of the undistilled product was 7 g. (87%); distilled product, 6 g. (73%). Found: Se, 36.51; OPr^i , 54.2. Calc. for $\text{OSe}(\text{OPr}^i)_2$: Se, 37.05; OPr^i , 55.15%].

n-Butyl Selenite.—Selenious acid (10 g.) was dissolved in excess of *n*-butanol. The reaction was endothermic. The contents were allowed to reflux under a column for about an hour (bath temp. $140-50^{\circ}$). The binary azeotrope of *n*-butanol and water (at 88°) was slowly collected. Refluxing was continued till the distilling liquid did not show any tendency of lowering the temperature below 115° . Excess of the alcohol was distilled. The contents were dried at the pump at the room temperature to afford a light yellow liquid distilling at $110^{\circ}/7\text{mm}$. Yield of the undistilled product was 16 g. (83%) and of the distilled product, 15 g (75%). Found: Se, 32.65. Calc. for $\text{OSe}(\text{OBu}^n)_2$: Se, 32.73%].

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